

East and southern Africa Coastal and ocean futures

*Future scenarios
for countries of the Western Indian
Ocean and the Northern Mozambique
Channel*

Contents

Executive Summary	1	Conclusion	11
Introduction	2	How to use the scenarios?	11
What are scenarios, and why do them?	2	Annexes background information	12
The Northern Mozambique Channel	2	1. Western Indian Ocean SDG 14 engagement, 2017-18.....	12
The scenarios.....	3	2. The Transformative Scenario Process (TSP).....	12
Uncertainties that vary between the scenarios..	3	3. Participants in the TSP process.....	13
Common elements across the scenarios.....	4		
The stories	5		
Slow but sure.....	7		
Riding the wave.....	8		
Pirate ship.....	9		
All pain no gain.....	10		

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Executive Summary

These scenarios have been developed for the countries of east and southern Africa, a region also known as the Western Indian Ocean. The United Nations Agenda 2030, the African Union's Agenda 2063 and the Nairobi Convention's vision all call for «*people of the region prospering from a healthy Western Indian Ocean*» based on economic development that «*conserves and sustainably uses the oceans, seas and marine resources*».

The challenge for these countries is how to achieve this in the increasingly complex world of the 21st century, when peoples' demands on the environment are outstripping nature's ability to provide and restore itself. Yet governments justifiably want and need economic growth to lift their people out of poverty and prosper as modern economies. This is encapsulated in the concept of the '*sustainable blue economy*', i.e. development driven by ocean wealth, conducted in sustainable ways to ensure long term benefits for all¹.

These scenarios focus on a subset of countries in the Northern Mozambique Channel, where the discovery of massive natural gas resources in some provides a plausible investment-driven pathway from low to middle or even high income status. But the outcome for citizens depends on the quality of governance and how wealth is shared. The scenarios thus focus on four options, contrasting high versus low governance and high versus low investment through four fictional countries over a single generation, from 2018-2035.

The stories use the metaphor of an ocean journey, evoking the potential wealth from the sea, the role of coastal and maritime trade in the countries' histories and futures, and the importance of ocean and coastal ecosystems in providing income and non-income benefits to people (such as livelihoods for the poor and adaptation to climate change). Their titles – 'slow but sure', 'riding the wave', 'pirate ship' and 'all pain no gain' - reflect aspects of both the excitement and the risks of sailing the seas.

The scenarios are intended as stimulus for discussion and debate in real policy and planning processes in east and southern Africa. As fictional stories, any reader may see elements from more than one scenario reflected in their country (or in the situation they are facing), as opposed to seeing a mirror of their country entirely in one scenario. The stories are designed to help provide signposts on individual decisions that in themselves may not seem significant, but when repeated year on year, and in sector after sector, influence the course of history towards one scenario or the other. The 'transformational' value of these scenarios is in helping decision-makers at all levels see how they can change the future, if they so want.

The scenarios also illustrate who 'wins' and who 'loses' in each case. This could help facilitate discussions about equity and delivering benefits 'for all' in the spirit of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)². The scenarios focus through SDG 14 on oceans, to explore how the full suite of SDGs may be delivered - via jobs, economic growth, health, education sustainable communities, and more. Running to 2035, the scenarios explore how countries may deliver on the SDGs and move into the post-2030 period to continue building on what they have achieved into a longer term future.

¹ http://d2ouvy59p0dg6k.cloudfront.net/downloads/15_1471_blue_economy_6_pages_final.pdf
² see Annex 1

Introduction

Scenarios must be:

Relevant

Illuminate current circumstances and concerns

Link into current mental models

Challenging

Make the invisible visible

Question current mental models

Plausible

Fact-based and logical

Improve systemic understanding

Clear

Distinct

Accessible and memorable

What are scenarios, and why do them?

Scenarios are alternative ways the future may unfold. They indicate possibilities that must be plausible and relevant. However, they are not predictions of the future, nor do they present a 'preferred future'. The scenarios here represent possible futures for coastal countries of east and southern Africa, but other futures may also be possible. These stories reflect the consensus of almost 100 people who participated in this process (see 3. *Participants in the TSP process*). They represent how the participants see the opportunities and challenges of the near future playing out in relation to the 'ocean economies' and coastal and marine systems of the countries of the region.

There are two main reasons for undertaking a scenario development process, and that led to this effort. Firstly, participants in the process have the chance to deepen their understanding of drivers of change and opportunities for decisions. This acknowledges that people are agents of change, and that individuals and groups of people can steer change in intentional ways. The participants in the scenario development process may thus become active agents of change in their respective domains, be that in government, their communities or in the private sector.

Second, scenarios can be used in planning and policy processes to help contextualize and rationalize the complex information and often competing interests at play. As 'thought experiments', scenarios are unlikely to represent the precise realities of different places and issues as the future unfolds. More likely, elements of one or more scenarios may be relevant to a particular context or set of stakeholders in a planning process. The degree to which the elements in a scenario are explained or can be understood in the context of existing drivers, and how they project the consequences of different choices into the future, may offer tangible options for understanding and negotiating tradeoffs among stakeholders. In this way, scenarios may potentially streamline planning and negotiation processes.

The Northern Mozambique Channel

These scenarios are focused on the developing countries of the Northern Mozambique Channel - a region emerging in global awareness as an important hotspot for the diversity and health of its marine ecosystems, and as a future source of natural gas. More broadly, however, the ocean systems, governance and economic context of these countries are shared by other countries of east and southern Africa (and indeed other African countries if one focuses on the principles, rather than the specifics).

Development of these scenarios was informed by the SDGs which establish a global agenda for sustainability from 2015-2030. Addressing the challenges of future poverty, environmental degradation and population growth will likely lie at the center of the partnership

initiative emerging between governments, communities, business and non-government organizations in the Northern Mozambique Channel.

These scenarios were developed to assist countries in implementing their commitments focused around SDG 14 on Oceans, which calls on people to conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources. They look past 2030, asking «what medium-term futures are possible given the current realities and future challenges and opportunities facing the region?»

This process is set in the established regional governance mechanism of the Nairobi Convention (more formally, the Convention for the Protection, Management and Development of the Marine and Coastal Environment of the Eastern African Region). Established through United Nations Environment's Regional Seas process and ratified in 1985, the Nairobi Convention sets a common vision among the 10 countries of the Western Indian Ocean region for protecting the living natural assets so essential to their socio-economic fabric. The SDGs provide a clarion call for ensuring that environmental sustainability, economic growth and human welfare are achieved together. A range of multi-country initiatives and funding mechanisms are converging around the common agenda provided by the SDGs to assure the future and long term prosperity of this region.

The scenarios herein describe hypothetical coastal countries in the Northern Mozambique Channel, a particular case study applicable to the broader contexts of the Western Indian Ocean and east and southern Africa.

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The scenarios

The four neighbouring countries presented in the scenarios have each been dealt a different hand of cards that influence the options they have and choices they make along their way. As much as they differ from one another, they also share commonalities. Any country in East Africa may recognize certain aspects of each of the four scenarios in their recent history or current circumstances.

The titles are evocative of an ocean journey – will the journey be beset by good or bad fortune, will the travelers reach the destination, and when? The ocean can be rich and generous, as well as fickle and unyielding. This metaphor speaks to the countries' histories and present - from ancient trade with far-off lands in spices, exotic foods ... and people ... carried on wooden ships powered by the wind; to modern containerized behemoths trading electronics and plastics ... and peoples' land and futures ... fuelled by oil and the chatter of digital networks. Whatever the level of technology or the age, success still depends on the wind and waves that rock the ship, on the skill of the captain and crew, and on the strength of the ship's rudder to direct it through whatever conditions prevail.

Uncertainties that vary between the scenarios

The scenarios open with the countries' 20th century experience of trade, leadership and social dynamics; their pathways from 2018 to 2035 are then affected by three sets of drivers:

a) Two **key uncertainties** that determine the four narratives: the level of governance (good versus poor, integration versus fragmentation) and the wealth and degree of investment (high versus low, from international and domestic sources);

b) A broader range of **secondary uncertainties**, including climate change, health and education, social and cultural norms and others: these create nuances among the stories, and are highlighted in the comparative table on the next page;

c) A range of key drivers that are **relatively certain** to occur and don't vary greatly between the countries. For example, population growth is reasonably certain to double national populations from 2015-2035 (see population charts at left, for all Western Indian Ocean countries). Similarly, climate change until 2035 is effectively 'locked in' (although we don't necessarily know how impacts will manifest), as current negotiations will affect long term climate, but not the changes anticipated in the next 20 years.

Common elements across the scenarios

Across the region - and indeed globally - the scale and diversity of human needs are overwhelming the ability of nature to provision people and sustain itself, so cracks are emerging. Within this context, the countries share many common elements, such as:

- The same **climate change** hazards, showing how strengths and weaknesses in governance and access to resources determine the type and scale of impacts experienced;
- **National populations are all growing** and the proportion of youth is high and rising. Coastal population growth is usually double the national average;
- **Coastal marine habitats** including coral reefs, mangroves, seagrass beds and coastal estuaries are shared across all countries, sustaining livelihoods and businesses (in, for example, fisheries and tourism) and reducing the impact of climate change hazards;
- **Historical trade and colonization**, first across the Indian Ocean and then by European powers, although each country experience has varied;
- The **transition under way in foreign investment and geopolitical influence** from Western countries and financial institutions to Asian investors (including, significantly, China's One Belt One Road initiative).

Scenario processes frequently start all narratives at the same point. However, given the range of histories of east and southern African countries and how these influence current and future possibilities, the stories presented here reflect embedded differences in history, resulting from similar drivers to those active today. In particular, the presence or lack of natural wealth and how that has influenced foreign engagement and the evolution of governance up to today plays a key role.

The stories

With two main axes representing high and low levels of governance and investment, the four scenarios cover four combinations:

1. High governance with low investment,
2. High governance with high investment,
3. Low governance with high investment,
4. Low governance with low investment.

These are reflected in the names:

Slow but sure - In this country there is little investment but governance is good. There is little wind and the progress of the ship is slow, but the crew are good and able to make the most of their situation.

Riding the wave - This country is blessed by rich resources and a good government. The wind is strong and steady, powering the ship forward, while the skilled captain and crew steer it expertly through the challenges en route.

Pirate ship - This country has abundant wealth but poor governance. The wind and waves are turbulent and rough, and the captain and crew act like pirates, uncaring of their passengers.

All pain no gain - This country is poor and poorly governed. With no resources or leadership it wallows without progressing, and all on board are dispirited.

How these major drivers play out against a backdrop of other drivers, common experiences and luck, are described in the narrative summaries on the next pages. The comparative table below provides a structured comparison of key narrative elements.

Comparative table of drivers across the four scenarios

Slow but sure

Riding the wave

Pirate ship

All pain no gain

Fisheries

Mix of small scale and commercial, with good management and compliance

Highly developed and managed, from small to large scale. Sustainable aquaculture developed.

Subsidized industrialized fleets damage poorly managed stocks. Aquaculture expanding with few controls

Fisheries mostly collapsed, driving traditional fishing communities into hardship, high urban migration

Coastal ecosystems

Strong co-management and restoration

High fragmentation, but being restored for multiple service values

Rampant destruction and fragmentation by coastal development

Degraded and fragmented by unsustainable uses and lack of management

Energy

High dependence on planted wood for charcoal, imported diesel

Natural gas used in low-carbon power generation, investing in renewables

High use of natural gas and diesel, no low-carbon innovation

Coal used in power generation and kitchens, wood and charcoal depleted.

Education

Good quality, innovative state education system, but with few resources

Universal education in state system, many private schools

Poor state education, many private schools, but of widely varying quality

Poor state education, low-quality private schools, few elite schools

Health

Good quality, rural/dispersed community clinics

Excellent hospitals and care from bottom to top, both state and private.

Public health system gutted by corruption, private care widely used but at high cost.

Outdated centralized hospitals, few and poor local clinics, no drugs. Elite go abroad for health care.

Social

Strong traditional institutions, transforming through modernization

Strong youth/civil society engagement with digital media, internationally connected

Social fabric broken by historical conflict, and ongoing state capture, high social conflict

Social fabric broken by tribal politics, absence of state-care, despair and disillusionment

Gender and youth

Traditional values modernizing through open dialogue

Modernization of social values and opportunities create space and opportunities for women and youth

Elite capture with little interest in social inclusion, neglect of girls education and youth development

Patriarchal values actively suppress women, youth, and minorities, no policies for inclusion.

Digital infrastructure

Internet and connectivity basic, but good mobile phone network coverage

High investment in digital infrastructure; lead in 4th industrial revolution in Africa

World-class connectivity in urban centres, but expensive and doesn't cater for the poor

One of the only profitable sectors so coverage reasonable, but quality poor and erratic.

Scenario 1

SLOW BUT SURE

A traditional, self-contained country that must transform and open up to face modern challenges, and meet the needs of its modernising, more connected and more educated youth. In this story the sea is becalmed, there is little wind and the progress of the ship is slow. But the captain, crew and tiller are good, and able to make the most of their situation.

This is a **difficult story of good governance and intentions**, held together by a strong cultural identity and pride, but facing continuous challenges due to limited resources. The older generation is increasingly out of touch, and a well-educated and intentioned youth start to take over. The age-old tensions between young and old play out, but both are able to compromise and move forward. Can the country modernize and finally attract better investment to support growth and a more outward focus?

GOVERNANCE

- Democratic government with strong grassroots.
- Focus on self reliance, history of low engagement with foreign trade and investment.
- Tensions between older and younger generations' values and vision.

ECOSYSTEMS

- Investment in repairing damage to natural assets pays off as key ecosystems regain health and productivity.
- Lack of resources limits the ability to invest in new technology for restoration, adaptation and preparedness.
- Sustainable use of resources threatened by growing population

SOCIAL & WELFARE

- Gender parity is reached in top government positions
- High quality public health and education services
- A typical family in 2030 lives in their rural home, adapted and modernized.
- Livelihoods are based on natural resources and community based enterprises

ECONOMY

- No oil and gas fields.
- Low level of investment and trade.
- Thriving but small scale community based and natural resource based enterprises.
- Remittances from diaspora significant

CLIMATE CHANGE

- Proactive in climate change adaptation and disaster preparedness
- Investment in ecosystem-based climate adaptation a core principle of national development.
- Intact coastal ecosystems and effective health services protect people from climate impacts

SDG TARGETS

- Making good progress in ocean sustainability (SDG14).
- High success in social and economic SDGs - hunger, health, education, gender, jobs, sustainable growth.
- A world leader in climate adaptation (SDG13) linked to achievement of environmental, social and economic SDG targets.

The future?

In this scenario the key challenges are a growing population combined with slow economic growth, resulting in insufficient opportunities for an increasingly frustrated youth.

- How could this country create new opportunities for its growing population?
- Can it open itself up to investment without compromising its strengths?
- How does good leadership persist when there are so many challenges?
- **What action could YOU take if you lived in this country?**

Scenario 2

RIDING THE WAVE

A country endowed with natural resources and wise leaders with long traditions, but forward-looking. Its population values its diversity from past and present exchange, and takes pride in its skills and prosperity. In this story the wind is strong and steady, powering the ship forward from one destination to another. The skilled crew and strong ship are up to the challenge, steering expertly through the challenges on the route.

The country **seems to have everything going for it** - good governance and financial means, broad based civil society engagement and attraction of long term committed investors offer multiple options and enable positive outcomes. From one destination to the next it takes in new ideas, new people, new technologies. Can the country maintain its good fortune as new tests emerge?

GOVERNANCE

- Democratic government with strong grassroots and technical capacity.
- Elections diminish in prominence as ethical professional standards spread across all political parties and minimum standards for social welfare are accepted by all.

ECOSYSTEMS

- Ecosystems degraded by construction and cyclone impacts restored as part of national 'blue' policies
- Investment in green-grey coastal defenses reduces costs of climate impacts and loss of human life.

SOCIAL & WELFARE

- Gender and youth empowerment supported in government programmes.
- Homes use gas for cooking and solar-roof tiles for energy.
- Affordable high quality health-care available to all in public and private systems.

ECONOMY

- Natural gas used for electricity generation in zero-carbon emission power plants.
- Profits from natural gas re-invested in dispersed renewable energy plants for rural/coastal urban locations
- The country has joined the BRICS as an emerging shining light in global development pathways

CLIMATE CHANGE

- Impacts from climate hazards managed successfully, through ecosystem-based risk reduction, coastal planning and health & social planning.
- The country plays a lead in climate negotiations, with SIDS and other leaders designing a new regime of Committed Nationally Determined Contributions (or CNDcs) by 2045.

SDG TARGETS

- In the top ten countries globally in achieving SDGs
- Full achievement of SDG14 targets, as well as of a comprehensive range of social and economic targets.

2 The future?

In this scenario the key challenges are the compounding of growth in incomes and population, and of maintaining good governance in the face of high wealth and opportunities, external pressures and immigration from other countries.

- Can this country maintain its good fortune and governance as new challenges emerge?
- Can it continue to balance economic growth, social welfare and ecosystem health?
- How can it best manage regional issues and immigration pressures?
- **What action could YOU take if you lived in this country?**

Scenario 3

PIRATE SHIP

A country endowed with riches that have attracted outsiders for centuries, creating a wealthy elite, but with little investment in social institutions and governance. In this story the wind is strong and turbulent, and waves are high. Without a strong rudder and captain the ship is buffeted from one side to another, losing people and cargo overboard, mindless to the losses.

With **new extreme wealth from natural gas, the country spirals towards state capture by the political and economic elite**, with a winner-takes-all economy and gated communities protecting the wealthy. Slums and poverty grow, as the environment and social capital decline. The riches provide many symbols of wealth and a source of national pride, but these are inaccessible to most. Who and what will fall overboard and be sacrificed in the journey through the next storm?

GOVERNANCE

- State capture by elites undermines democratic processes.
- Severe civil unrest results from climate impacts in 2032-33 and elite capture of state resources.
- Demonstrations suppressed violently by state and private security forces.

ECOSYSTEMS

- Over 80% of coastal habitats lost to coastal construction and absence of spatial planning.
- Persistent low-oxygen dead zones and fish die-offs become frequent, the first for the region.
- Subsidized poorly managed fishing degrades marine fishery stocks.

SOCIAL & WELFARE

- The Human Development Index declines from 2020-2035.
- A typical home is mud-walled, corrugated iron-roofed hut on unpaved paths, in rural and slum areas.
- Child mortality rates high and low government support for health, education and women's rights.

ECONOMY

- Vast wealth created from natural gas extraction, but heavily concentrated in business and government elites.
- Energy sector based on fossil fuel extraction and use (gas, diesel, kerosene).
- No investment is made in renewable sources or efficient distribution infrastructure for low income areas.

CLIMATE CHANGE

- Flooding and cyclone damage to constructed coastlines very high.
- Disease epidemics and hunger kill over 100,000 slum dwellers for 2 years after cyclone Hasira.
- The country emerges as one of the largest African contributors to greenhouse gas emissions.

SDG TARGETS

- The country stayed away from the UN SDG Summit in 2030.
- Declining performance on most SDG Targets from 2020-2030
- Engagement by international community in civil rights investigations (SDG 16) from 2033 bring chance for change.

The future?

In this scenario the key challenge is the concentration of power and wealth in an elite that is increasingly distanced from the large and growing base of the societal pyramid, and disenchantment among millions of disenfranchised youth.

- How can this country share its prosperity more equally?
- Can a new generation of leaders emerge?
- What role can civil society and regional or international actors play?
- Can technology improve the situation?
- **What action could YOU take if you lived in this country?**

Scenario 4

ALL PAIN NO GAIN

A country with few natural resources, struggling to advance. Petty political conflicts dominate, fuelled by tribal populist leaders with no governance vision for the country. In this story there is no wind to power the ship forward, and the captain and crew lack the skills and are dispirited. The poor fortune onboard breeds a culture of laziness, and the ship wallows and stagnates.

With **few assets to capitalize and little technical or political ability** to make the most of even the rich marine and coastal habitats, the country attracts second-tier and 'shark' investors out to make a quick return, and with no interest in long term shared benefits. The country spirals down, into a failed state syndrome, with crisis upon crisis draining national resources and democratic engagement, falling farther behind in the 21st century. What and who will ever start the country moving in a meaningful direction?

GOVERNANCE

- Leadership vacuum created by tribalist, populist leaders without a national vision or ability to inspire all to a common cause.
- State resources traded and squandered by politicians on politicized and poorly planned flagship projects that repeatedly fail.
- Collapse of democratic processes in 2033 and approaching condition of a failed state in 2035.

ECOSYSTEMS

- Coastal ecosystems and resources collapse after fragmentation from growing demand, misuse and lack of coastal planning.
- Failure to invest in ecosystem-based management and principles results in declining ecosystem service provision to and increased vulnerability of the poorest households.

SOCIAL & WELFARE

- Minority, women's and childrens rights neglected, leading to disenfranchised groups
- By 2035, infant, child and maternal mortality rates rise to 2-5x 2000 levels.
- Outbreaks of malaria, yellow fever, cholera and chikungunya flare up like clockwork. Malnutrition and growth-stunting affect more than one half of children, with significant effects on attendance and performance in primary schools.
- 40% of boys out of school by age 13, 50% for girls.

ECONOMY

- The country ranks in the lowest 10 worldwide for GDP and HDI.
- Strikes across the public sector due to non-payment of wages extend to military in 2032.

CLIMATE CHANGE

- Zero investment in climate resilience and adaptation.
- Cyclone Hasira, flooding and drought in 2032-33 create food shortages, water wars and hunger, impacting 20 million people.
- 200,000 deaths attributed to climate-related epidemics.

SDG TARGETS

- Declines in HDI and SDG indicators are suspected across the board, but due to lack of underlying data no statistics are available.

The future?

In this scenario the key challenges are the lack of interest and ability in good governance, and in technical and economic fields to advance with resources that are available.

- How can this country pause, take stock and transform itself?
- What pillars for governance and social equity need to be put in place?
- What role can civil society and regional or international actors play?
- Can new technologies improve the situation?
- **What action could YOU take if you lived in this country?**

Conclusion

There is clearly a country that has been 'dealt the best hand of cards' - where governance and investment are both good, or high - and another which has the worst hand, where governance and investment are both low. But each country can make its own decisions based on their cards - their fate is not determined only by their cards. There are nuances across the stories, and elements that a reader might recognize from his or her country or a neighbour today, in the recent past, or imaginable in the near future.

Which elements are desirable, and which can we influence by choices made today, to achieve the 'future we want'? What choices improve a country's hand, and help it transition to a better future? What choices worsen a country's hand, and shift it towards a worse future? And, importantly, in each case who wins and who loses? Is it possible to identify solutions in which a greater number of people win, along with the environment, and potentially no-one loses?

The metaphor of the ocean journey captures the uncertainties of a country's development pathway, and that there is always another step to be made. So the scenarios all end with further questions (at left). These revolve around improvements or regressions in governance or investment, trends and interactions with other drivers, and consequences on population growth, education, welfare and myriad other factors.

How to use the scenarios?

These scenarios are useful for different actors to consider how they may respond to a given situation, based on where they are placed. They are a call to action, to help individual actors respond and act, in whatever sector, type of institution or set of issues they are faced with.

The regional context in which the scenarios have been developed is the Nairobi Convention and the Western Indian Ocean, and the importance of sustaining ocean ecosystems to achieve what is increasingly called a '**sustainable blue economy**' - economic prosperity based on ocean resources that conserves and protects those resources as the foundation for social wellbeing and economic growth. This is the core message of Sustainable Development Goal 14 on oceans. The scenarios could help state and non-state actors implement the Voluntary Commitments they made to achieve SDG14 at the UN Ocean Conference in 2017 (see Annex 1).

At national levels, the different drivers and consequences highlighted by the scenarios need to be considered in marine spatial planning processes and to achieve integrated ocean governance. The scenarios can provide a framework for alignment among sectors, stakeholders and countries.

Further work will explore more deeply the implications of each scenario, and in their quantification using suitable indicators (such as GDP, ecosystem health and SDG indicators), to reveal more explicitly the implications of decisions within national and regional policy processes.

KEY QUESTIONS

Slow but sure

- How could this country create new opportunities for its growing population?
- Can it open itself up to investment without compromising its strengths?
- How does good leadership persist when there are so many challenges?
- What action could you take if you lived in this country?

Riding the Wave

- Can this country maintain its good fortune and governance as new challenges emerge?
- Can it continue to balance economic growth, social welfare and ecosystem health?
- How can it best manage regional issues and immigration pressures?
- What action could you take if you lived in this country?

Pirate Ship

- How can this country share its prosperity more equally?
- Can a new generation of leaders emerge?
- What role can civil society and regional or international actors play?
- Can technology improve the situation?
- What action could you take if this scenario plays out in your country?

All Pain no Gain

- How can this country pause, take stock and transform itself?
- What pillars for governance and social equity need to be put in place?
- What role can civil society and regional or international actors play?
- Can new technologies improve the situation?
- What action could you take if this scenario plays out in your country?

Annexes

background information

Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development

1. Western Indian Ocean SDG 14 engagement, 2017-18

The countries of the Northern Mozambique Channel have made significant strides toward advancing the regional agenda for SDG14. Decision makers have embarked on a multi-stakeholder journey using a partnership approach to define a joint vision and identify means of implementation for SDG14. This approach was highlighted as key to achieving the SDG14 targets in the Western Indian Ocean both at the Preparatory Workshop hosted by the Seychelles in May 2017 and during the UN Ocean Conference in June 2017. There, countries and organizations from the region presented joint Voluntary Commitments towards enhancing regional collaboration around sustainable ocean management and meeting the SDG14 targets³.

The process was continued during two further SDG14 workshops, hosted by the Government of Mozambique in Maputo (November 2017) and by the Government of Tanzania in Zanzibar (March 2018). This series of workshops brought together key regional stakeholders to produce the four scenario narratives. The workshops further served to lay down key next steps for collaboration toward achieving the SDG14 targets in the Northern Mozambique Channel as well as more broadly in the Western Indian Ocean, based on the principles of integrated ocean management and the sustainable blue economy. Final validation of the scenarios and their role in helping countries deliver on their SDG14 Voluntary Commitments is expected through the Nairobi Convention processes for its 9th Conference of Parties and the Science-Policy forum established by the Convention, in July/August 2018.

2. The Transformative Scenario Process (TSP)

TSP is an approach that brings concerned stakeholders from different, often competing, perspectives together around sets of pressing problems to build narratives that illustrate a range of potential futures. TSP places significant importance on convening as diverse a group as possible, and pays attention to the different normative views influencing the scenarios. Emphasis is placed on scenarios as conversation starters toward deeper understanding and more collaborative action for change. As such, scenarios are not the primary outcome. Although they are useful as a product co-produced by a diverse group of people, more ambitious and longer-term outcomes are shared understanding and stronger collaboration between influential role-players who have historically worked in parallel or at cross-purposes.

TSP can impact directly on the participants of the scenario process by transforming how they think about the issues, risks and trade-offs, by developing a deeper common understanding, and growing and deepening relationships amongst the scenario team. These aspects in turn enable participants to develop new strategic responses, enter into strategic conversations and collaborate with others toward enabling such strategies in a way that might not have been possible previously.

TSP typically involves the establishment of a diverse convening team; undertaking in-depth interviews to elicit their most pressing concerns and questions; undertaking 2 to 3 multi-day workshops with this group to first begin to construct the scenarios and then to consider the implications and strategic responses for both adapting to and shaping the future. The scenario writing and production occurs between the workshops, and is a deliberately collaborative and transparent process that requires sign-off by the entire scenario team before they can be launched. As co-produced outputs they are necessarily simplified, and their true value and expression lies in the ongoing thought, deliberation and decision-making that we hope will ensue.

³ For further information, see <https://oceanconference.un.org/>

3. Participants in the TSP process

We would like to acknowledge the participants in the TSP and Voluntary Commitment workshops:

Comoros: Ambadi Issouf, Mhamoudou Abidina, Mohammed Said Mikandjile Abdel Malik, Said Boina, Saidou Oumeira.

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Further references/to look at:

The scenarios: www.wiofutures.net

Background information: www.cordioea.net/nmc/scenarios

The approach: <http://reospartners.com/tools/transformation-scenarios/>

Some other examples of TSP processes:

- Land Reform (South Africa) - <http://www.landreformfutures.org>
- Education (Brazil) - <http://cenarioseducacao2032.org.br>
- Food system (South Africa) - <http://www.thefutureoffood.co.za>
- Democracy (Latin America) - <http://www.alertademocratica.org>
- Political transformation (South Africa) <http://www.dinokengscenarios.co.za>

